

MOTIVATION AND TIME MANAGEMENT PRACTICES ADOPTED BY TEACHERS FOR QUALITY ASSURANCE IN PUBLIC AND PRIVATE SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN ENUGU STATE

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Abstract: *This study comparatively analyzed the motivation and time management practices adopted by teachers for quality assurance in public and private secondary schools in Enugu State. Two specific purposes, two research questions, and two hypotheses guided the study. Descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The population comprised 22,480 secondary school teachers in the 885 secondary schools comprising 299 public secondary schools and 586 private secondary schools in Enugu state. A total of 1,124 teachers made up of 367 public secondary school teachers and 757 private secondary school teachers from 45 schools in the study area, representing 5% of the population were sampled using multistage sampling procedure. A structured questionnaire, “Classroom Management Practices Adopted by Teachers for Quality Assurance Questionnaire (CMPATQA) was used for data collection. The instruments were face validated by three experts. Internal consistency coefficients of 0.81 and 0.80 was obtained for CMPATQA using Cronbach’s Alpha statistical method. The researchers administered copies of the instrument to the respondents with the help of six research assistants. Data were analyzed using Mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions and t-test statistics was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings revealed that public secondary school teachers agreed on one of the adoption of motivation practices while private secondary school teachers disagreed on time management practices. From the results of the hypotheses, significant difference was established in the adoption of motivation practices while no significant difference was established in the other variable of the study. Based on the findings, the researcher recommend: teachers’ recognition of students’ achievements and utilization of positive reinforcement to sustain students’ motivation for quality assurance; post primary school management board organization of programs that equip teachers with knowledge and skills for effective lesson planning and class scheduling, emphasizing the use of contemporary techniques and tools for teachers’ adequate prioritization of classroom task in public and private secondary schools in Enugu State.*

Introduction

One of the greatest challenges facing teachers in

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the classroom is that of motivating the students to learn. Motivation is the process that account for an individual's direction, intensity and persistence of effort towards attaining a goal. Motivation practices in the classroom describes the strategies teachers adopt to encourage both themselves and the students they teach to achieve educational goals. The teachers play important role in the motivation of students for improved learning. This is in line with the thoughts of Agatha (2015), that teachers are the key components of providing high-quality education, which is the solution to many problems in our challenging and complex society. Hung (2020) is of the view that when teachers are motivated, they render quality services, increases their performance and commitments to their jobs, motivate their students to learn and consequently help guarantee high quality education. Effective classroom management practices, that promote educational quality assurance, are more likely to be adopted by motivated teachers. Teachers' motivational practices are essential to both their effectiveness in the classroom, the motivation of students and the quality of education they deliver. A motivated teacher will work harder, try new techniques, activities and practices, and in general do more for the sake of the learners (Gokce, 2010). Motivated teachers significantly influence their students' attitudes toward learning. Teachers who are passionate and committed are more likely to adopt innovative teaching techniques and classroom management practices including effective communication, consistent instructional monitoring, inspiring motivation and efficient time management in order to grab students' attention and maintain it. This is in line with the opinion of Zou H et al.

(2023) that teachers who feel competent, independent, and appreciated are more likely to encourage intrinsic motivation in their students. Hence, by fostering a supportive and engaging learning environment in the classroom, motivated teachers significantly influence their students' attitudes toward learning. Students' motivation generally determines their level of involvement in the teaching activities. However, since motivation is an internal, psychological process that cannot be seen or touched, its presence or absence can be deduced from the students' observable behavior of students in the classroom (Azim et al., 2021). When students are highly motivated and adequate attention given to them, they pay attention to classroom instruction and it adds value to the education quality by raising the quality of teaching and learning process. The motivation practices adopted by teachers to provide a conducive learning environment helps to satisfy the individual needs of their students. These will also encourage changes in practices, behavior, perception and attitude of students leading to high morale and improved academic achievement for quality assurance in schools. In addition, teachers' motivation practices have an enormous impact on how well they manage their classrooms as motivated teachers motivate or inspire their students by adopting efficient classroom management practices which foster a conducive learning environment and promote quality assurance in secondary schools. Motivation being an essential classroom management practice that is explored in this study is a force that pushes an individual towards the initiation of certain activities and determines the level of effort to be put into such activities for

sustenance towards achieving a goal. Browne (2013) emphasized the use of positive reinforcement as an effective classroom motivation strategy. This according to him includes the use of a token, praise; tangible reward etcetera as reinforcer to strengthen positive behavior in the classroom. Adequate motivation will promote teachers' utilization of classroom management practices and the provision of necessary support that ensure that students are learning in a timely manner. If the teachers have low motivation to work due to inefficient use of time in the classroom, it will negatively affect them resulting in increased stress and burnout and subsequently lead to the delivery of disorganized lessons that results in inconsistent learning outcomes that undermines the attainment of quality assurance in schools. Hence the need for proper time management in the classroom.

Time management is a classroom practice that has assisted teachers to organize themselves for delivery of well-structured lessons that promote students' engagement and learning outcomes. Time management is the process of planning and exercising conscious control of the time spent on specific activities (Marika, Jagero, Kanga and Gitari, 2021). This is in line with the view of Uwazuruike and Anyaogu (2020) defined time management as the way that staff use their period effectively in carrying out their work without exceeding the fixed calendar.

Time management play an important role in meeting the immediate needs of the students and ensuring quality assurance in the education system. Effective secondary school administration rests on time management abilities of the administrators to ensure better

work performance of teachers in workplace (Ekanem, 2015). Time should be valued and spent in a reasonable manner in the classroom. This will enable teachers to plan the classroom lessons and apply strategies that will help maximize time and promote learning amongst students. In support of the above assertion is the view of Mehta (2019) that setting of priorities is one of the most important task in the classroom. Mehta further stated that important strategies for classroom time management as: Defining objectives for each lesson and remaining focused on them; being flexible; reviewing the assigned material even if it has been taught; allowing time for questioning on difficult concepts; writing the lesson plan; keeping the classroom dynamic in mind; prioritizing established task to cover most important concepts; using time controlled activities like group work promote quality teaching and learning in the classroom.

Teachers should employ time management practices in the management of their classrooms for improved standard because time is a scarce resources and time is that quality of nature which keeps all events from happening at once. Akinfolarin (2017) posits that when school administrators are effective in managing their time, the school will highly benefit from their means use of time management as a means of fostering administrative effectiveness. No wonder Kalu (2012) concluded that time management increases efficiency and productivity. Ajayi (2020) went further to outline the benefits of maximizing time for effective administration and control as: facilitates delegation of duties to staff; reduction of misunderstanding on essential duties; creates opportunity for carrying out task; reduce conflicts

in schedules and facilitate meeting of deadlines. Adequate management of time in the school enhances teachers' coverage of scheme of work which invariably improve students' academic performance. This is in line with the view of Adebayo and Omojola (2012) is of the view that the teaching staff can decide which tasks fall into the categories of essential task, important task and low value task by deciding which tasks are most valuable to the school. Time is a valuable but yet limited resource hence teachers' adequate management of time in the classroom will help to improve students understanding of lessons taught, promoting consistency in the quality of education provided in schools. Effective management of time in the classroom help teachers to maximize instructional periods, create a structured learning environment, guarantee that the content is delivered in its entirety, and improves student attention and involvement. Adequate time management can be achieved by setting goals and prioritizing future work based on the individual or schools' move towards meeting the set goals and objectives of learning. Ultimately, teachers' adoption of this practice will provide students with necessary academic assistance, get them ready for success and strengthen the attainment of quality assurance in education.

Quality assurance involves all the processes that contribute to the success of the end-product (the learner) in terms of the learning outcome. Quality assurance is about continuous improvement in the teaching-learning process. Ayeni (2010) describes quality assurance in education as the systematic management, monitoring and evaluation of performance of school administrators, teachers and students against

educational goals to ensure consistent documentation, review and decision towards quality improvement in institutional management, teaching and learning processes for the achievement of set standards in schools. Therefore, there is the need that all stakeholders in the implementation process must play appropriate roles to ensure that the end-products of the process will be geared towards realizing the expected quality encapsulated in the goals of education.

Public and private secondary schools seem not to be providing quality education to the expected level because as important as education is to the citizens in Nigeria, it is still experiencing challenges that prevent equal access and quality assurance (Atanda and Olaifa, 2022), Hence, the achievement of quality assurance in education will be greatly enhanced if teachers in Nigeria's public and private secondary schools, including those in Enugu State, utilize a variety of classroom management practices. However, the situation in some public and private secondary schools in Enugu State raise questions about whether or not teachers actually adopt classroom management practices in their teaching in secondary schools in the state.

Statement of the Problem

Classroom management is the bedrock of teaching and learning in any country. Nigerian public and private school teachers need to be efficient in handling classroom management issues to produce quality students who will compete with their counterparts in other parts of the world. Teachers are expected to be motivation specialists and time managers for a variety of curriculum-related and extracurricular activities to achieve this goal. Despite the

important role of teachers in classroom management at all levels of education, some public and private secondary school teachers in the area of study seem not to be utilizing effective motivation and time management practices which may negatively affect student learning outcomes in public and private schools, as it does not allow students active participation in the learning process and classroom activities. In turn, students' ability to gain quality knowledge is needed to meet set standards for quality assurance in education.

Considering that public secondary schools in the area of study appear to be dealing with classroom management issues of overcrowding and low student engagement which seems to be higher in public schools. These issues may be affecting the quality of instruction and holistic educational experience of students in the state's public secondary schools, as seen by the increase in private secondary schools and the apparent preference of parents and guardians for private schools. However, private schools appear to excel in areas such as managing time effectively, providing instructional support to students, and multitasking. On the other hand, the excessive focus of private schools on profit-making seem to hurt staff professional development, as the quality of teachers are questionable, with high rate of teacher stress and burnout which in turn affects the educational standards.

Furthermore, it is disturbing that a number of low motivation indicators are prevalent in both public and private secondary schools in Enugu state. These include reduced student participation in learning activities, teachers' procrastination and resistance to feedback. Hence, the attainment of quality assurance in

secondary schools in Enugu state is unlikely to occur if this trend is not rectified. In addition, there seems to be a paucity of empirical studies on the comparative analysis of classroom management practices adopted by teachers for quality assurance in public and private secondary schools in the area of study, hence the need for this study. The problem of the study is: Do public secondary schools adopt motivation and time management practices for quality assurance more effectively than their private school counterparts in Enugu state.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study was to comparatively analyze the classroom management practices adopted by teachers for quality assurance in public and private secondary schools in Enugu state. Specifically, the study compared the;

1. Motivation practices adopted by teachers in public and private secondary schools in Enugu State for quality assurance.
2. Time management practices adopted by teachers in public and private secondary schools in Enugu state for quality assurance.

Research Questions

The following questions were raised to provide answers for the study:

1. What are the motivation practices adopted by teachers in public and private secondary schools for quality assurance in Enugu State?
2. What are the time management practices adopted by teachers in public and private secondary schools for quality assurance in Enugu State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated for the study and were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

1. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of teachers in public and private secondary schools in Enugu State on motivation practices for quality assurance.

2. There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of teachers in public and private secondary schools in Enugu State on the time management practices used for quality assurance.

Method

Descriptive survey research design was adopted for this study. The study was conducted in Enugu State, Nigeria. The population of the study comprised 22,480 secondary school teachers (7,343 Public and 15, 137 private) in the 885 secondary schools comprising 299 public secondary schools and 586 private secondary schools in Enugu state. The sample size of the study was 1,124 teachers made up of 367 public secondary school teachers and 757 private secondary school teachers from 45 schools (5% of the population) drawn using multistage sampling technique. Structured questionnaires titled: “Classroom Management Practices adopted by Teachers for Quality Assurance Questionnaire (CMPATQAQ)” was used for data collection. The instruments were face validated by three experts in the Faculty of Education Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka. Internal consistency co-efficient of 0.87 and 0.96 were obtained for CMPATQAQ

using Cronbach’s Alpha statistical method. The researchers administered the instrument to the research participants with the help of six research assistants. Out of the 1,124 copies distributed, 1,087 copies from 351 public and 736 private secondary school teachers were returned duly completed, and used for data analysis. Descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions. The mean scores were used to interpret the data by categorizing the results into levels using Cohen (2013) range of values, thus: 1.00-1.50, very low extent; 1.51-2.50, low extent; 2.51-3.50 moderate extent; 3.51-4.50, high extent, and 4.51-5.00, very high extent. The t-test was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The decision rule was: a null hypothesis was not rejected where the calculated p-value was greater than the stipulated level of significance value (0.05). The reverse is the case where the calculated p-value was less than the stipulated level of significance. All analyses were carried out using Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) Version 25.

Results

Research Question One: What are the motivation practices adopted by teachers in public and private secondary schools for quality assurance in Enugu State?

Table 1: Mean Ratings of Respondents on the Motivation Practices Adopted By Teachers in Public and Private Secondary Schools in Enugu State for Quality Assurance

S/N Items	Public (n=351)			Private (n=736)		
	Mean	SD	Remark	Mean	SD	Remark
1. Make use of non-verbal cues to support instruction	3.02	.68	Agree	3.08	.67	Agree
2. Make use of praise and recognition to encourage students effort	2.86	.62	Agree	2.90	.65	Agree
3. Recommend well behaved or best performed students in your class for recognition or award in the school	2.81	.67	Agree	2.82	.72	Agree
4. Reinforce positive behaviour with the use of tokens and gifts	2.94	.72	Agree	2.99	.77	Agree
5. Use humour to stimulate students' interest or reduce classroom tension	3.16	.66	Agree	3.22	.70	Agree
6. Make use of reward systems to motivate students	2.80	.66	Agree	2.81	.73	Agree
7. Give feedback to the students on their performance and behaviour	2.94	.72	Agree	3.01	.76	Agree
8. Integrate technology and multimedia resources to make lessons more engaging and relevant	3.16	.66	Agree	3.22	.70	Agree
9. Make use of punishment whenever there is misbehaviour in your class	2.99	.69	Agree	3.15	.76	Agree
10. Connect classroom learning to real-world applications and experiences to enhance students motivation	2.87	.66	Agree	2.94	.73	Agree
11. Set clear goals and expectations for students and help them track their progress	2.94	.70	Agree	2.91	.74	Agree
12. Incorporate interactive and collaborative learning experiences to foster students engagement	3.06	.68	Agree	3.16	.67	Agree
13. Pay extra attention to a student who is not performing well in your class	3.07	.73	Agree	3.06	.72	Agree

Table 1 shows the mean ratings of respondents on the motivation practices adopted by teachers in public and private secondary schools for quality assurance in Enugu State. The findings of the

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study showed that teachers from public and private secondary schools adopted all the motivation practices for quality assurance. This means that teachers from public and private secondary schools use praise well and recommend well behaved students, reinforce positive behaviour, adopt use of reward, give feedback, use punishment, use real world

application, set clear goals, help students to track their progress and pay extra attention to non-performing students in class for quality assurance.

Research Question Two: What are the time management practices adopted by teachers in public and private secondary schools for quality assurance?

Table 2: Mean Ratings of Respondents on the Time Management Practices Adopted By Teachers in Public and Private Secondary Schools in Enugu State for Quality Assurance

S/N	Items	Public (n=351)			Private (n=736)		
		Mean	SD	Remark	Mean	SD	Remark
14.	Make use of the class time effectively	2.12	.79	Disagree	2.81	.73	Agree
15.	Organize classroom activities to effectively manage transitions between activities	2.21	.87	Disagree	2.99	.77	Agree
16.	Coordinate students' responses to effectively manage class time during class discussions	2.27	.89	Disagree	3.21	.71	Agree
17.	Prioritize and plan instruction to accommodate review sessions in the classroom	2.30	.88	Disagree	3.10	.77	Agree
18.	Ensure adequate management of class time during group work	2.56	.75	Agree	2.94	.73	Agree
19.	Organize class activities to balance direct instruction and independent work time	2.74	.96	Agree	3.18	.71	Agree
20.	Utilize time management strategies to keep students on their task in the classroom	2.89	.72	Agree	3.19	.77	Agree
21.	Strategically manage class time during assessments	2.97	.73	Agree	2.98	.74	Agree
22.	Balance the time between providing individualized support to students and managing the overall classroom environment	3.24	.74	Agree	3.22	.70	Agree
23.	Involve students in managing their time during classroom instruction and assignment	2.86	.74	Agree	3.16	.76	Agree
24.	Employ techniques to stay organized and minimize time wastage during classroom instruction	3.00	.73	Agree	2.94	.73	Agree

25. Provide opportunities for students to practice and apply knowledge gained in the classroom 2.63 .93 Agree 3.19 .71 Agree

Table 2 shows respondents’ mean rating on time management practices adopted by teachers in public and private secondary schools for quality assurance in Enugu State. The mean ratings for public secondary school teachers on all the 12 items ranged from 2.12 to 3.24 while that of private school teachers ranged from 2.81 to 3.22. This means that time management is better adopted in private secondary schools than public

secondary schools in Enugu State.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis One; There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of teachers in public and private secondary schools in Enugu State on the motivation practices adopted for quality assurance.

Table 3: t-test Summary of the Ratings of Public and Private Secondary School Teachers on the Motivation Practices Used for Quality Assurance

Source of variation	N	\bar{X}	SD	Df	t-cal	P-value	Remark
Public	351	2.97	.28	1085	2.43	.06	Not-Sig
Private	736	3.02	.34				

The analysis of the test of hypothesis one in Table 3 show that the mean score for public secondary school teachers ($M=2.97$, $SD=.28$) is not significantly less than that of those in private schools ($M=3.02$, $SD=.34$); $t(1085) = 2.43$, $p=.06$. The null hypothesis of no significant difference between the two groups on the

motivation practices adopted for quality assurance in Enugu State is not rejected.

Hypothesis Two; There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of teachers in public and private secondary schools in Enugu State on the time management practices used for quality assurance.

Table 4: t-test Summary of the Ratings of Public and Private Secondary School Teachers on the Time Management Practices Used for Quality Assurance

Source of variation	N	\bar{X}	SD	Df	t-cal	P-value	Remark
Public	351	3.00	.37	1085	2.65	.00	Sig
Private	736	3.07	.45				

Table 4 show that the mean score for public secondary school teachers ($M=3.00$, $SD=.37$) is significantly less than that of those in private schools ($M=3.07$, $SD=.45$); $t(1085) = 2.65$, $p=.00$. The null hypothesis of no significant difference between the two groups on the time management practices adopted for quality assurance in Enugu State was therefore rejected.

Discussion of Findings

Motivation Practices Adopted By Teachers in Public and Private Secondary Schools

The findings in Table 1 on the motivation practices adopted by teachers in public and private secondary schools for quality assurance showed that motivation is adopted at a high extent in both public and private secondary schools in Enugu State. Similarly, the results in Table 3 indicated that there is no significant difference between the adoption of motivation practices by public and private secondary school teachers in Enugu State. The interpretation of the findings is that when teachers in public and private secondary schools in Enugu State consistently adopt the practice of motivation in their classroom management, this will result to students meeting learning standards in the schools for the attainment of quality assurance. The findings of the study agreed with Zou H *et*

al (2023) who emphasized that teachers that feel competent are more likely to encourage intrinsic motivation in their students. . The findings of the study on reinforcement of positive behaviour conform to Azim *et al* (2021) that teachers' motivation can be deduced from the students' observable behavior in the classroom since motivation is an internal psychological process that can't be seen or touched. Hence, positive behavior of students promotes classroom engagement and academic achievement of students raising the quality of education. The findings also agreed with Browne (2013) that teachers' use of effective classroom motivation practices promotes positive behavior that encourages students to learn. The findings on paying extra attention to non-performing students is in line with Akunne and Nwadinobi (2023) that teachers' motivation particularly in terms of intrinsic factors increases job satisfaction and in turn positively impacts students' performance. The findings of the study is not a surprise given the effort that education stakeholders are making towards the development of teachers in the state.

Regarding the difference between the extent of adoption of motivation practices for quality assurance in public and private secondary schools, the results as displayed in Table 3

indicated that there is no significant difference between the extent of adoption of motivation practices by teachers in public and private secondary schools in Enugu State. This indicates that teachers from both school types acknowledged the importance of encouraging and inspiring students to promote active participation and improve academic performance. When motivation is consistently utilized, students are more likely to develop favourable attitude towards learning, remain engaged in class activities and attain better learning outcomes. This shared commitment to motivation improves the teaching and learning environment and contributes to the sustenance of high standards of education in secondary schools.

Time Management Practices Adopted By Teachers in Public and Private Secondary Schools in Enugu State for Quality Assurance.

Findings on the difference between the adoption of time management practices by teachers in public and private secondary schools as displayed in Table 2 revealed that time management is adopted at a high extent in private secondary schools than public secondary schools in Enugu State. The findings in Table 4 also showed that there is a significant difference between the mean ratings of teachers in public secondary schools and private secondary schools on time management practices for quality assurance in Enugu State. The findings of the study on the issue of teachers' organization of class activities is in line with that of Mehta (2019) who reported that teachers' setting of priorities is one of the most important strategies for classroom time management which promotes

quality teaching and learning in schools. The findings of the study on teachers' minimizing time wastage is consistent with Kalu (2012) who posits that time management increases efficiency and productivity. The findings on the use of time management strategies by teachers is in line with Adebayo and Omojola (2012) opinion that teachers' decision of which task falls into the categories of essential task, important task, and low-value task is essential for setting goals and prioritizing work for quality assurance in secondary schools. The findings on teachers' balancing time between individualized support to students and managing overall class environment aligned with Uwazuruike and Anyaogu (2020) who found that time management is a practice that ensures that teachers use their class period effectively in carrying out their duties of imparting knowledge without exceeding the fixed calendar. The findings on the involvement of students in management of their time agreed with Nasrullah and Khan (2015) in their submission that successful students are good at time planning and time management which reflects positively in their academic performance. The disparity in the findings of the study implies that public secondary schools experience challenges like slow lesson pacing, not covering the whole syllabus, and reduced instructional effectiveness which can have a negative impact on students' performance. On the other hand, private secondary school teachers that consistently adopt time management practices will experience improved lesson delivery, better utilize their instructional time and achieve their learning objectives more often. To ensure equity and fairness in educational outcomes, public

secondary teachers needs to enhance their time management skills through training and supervision in order to conform to best practices that promote quality assurance across public and private secondary schools.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, it was found that there is no difference in the extent of adoption of motivation practices as both public and private secondary school teachers adopted motivation practices. However, there is a variation in the extent of adoption of time management practices between public and private secondary school teachers for quality assurance as private secondary school teachers adopted time management practices more than public secondary school teachers in Enugu State. The study concluded that the adoption of classroom management practices of motivation and time management by public and private secondary school teachers is a valuable practice for promoting quality assurance in secondary

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schools in Enugu State.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made.

1. Teachers should adopt various methods of motivation in their classrooms to arouse interest and promote student engagement during learning. They should also recognize students' achievements and utilize positive reinforcement to sustain students' motivation for improved learning outcome.

2. Post Primary School Management Board should regularly organize programs that focus on equipping teachers with the knowledge and skills required for effective lesson planning and classroom scheduling emphasizing the utilization of contemporary techniques and tools that help teachers to prioritize classroom task adequately in both public and private secondary schools

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